

CREATING EXPLAINABLE SUMMARIES FOR LONG SCIENTIFIC DOCUMENTS USING LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS

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Abstract

This paper proposes a system intended for the summarization of long scientific documents, with particular emphasis being placed on accuracy, coherence, and transparency to create trustable summaries through the combination of a large language model with an explanation mechanism. The primary goal of this system is to help users efficiently acquire the most significant information from scientific papers for applications and use cases related to science search. The resulting system was evaluated with two user studies to measure the quality of the resulting summaries and the efficiency of the system's explanation functionality, as well as its impact on trustability of the systems. Although the results were generally promising, there was a high deviation in the ratings for some metrics, indicating that further research is needed to provide reliable and consistent performance.

INTRODUCTION

With the increase in content available on the Web showing no sign of slowing, it has become an unavoidable source of information for its users. Although this vast amount of information opens up new opportunities, it can also present challenges. Search engines are becoming increasingly indispensable on a Web that encompasses more content than anyone could ever sift through, with people recognizing the potential for trouble in this situation. Facilitating access to information involves securing its availability and delivery. With most search engines based on very few indices until now, the question of retrieval and potential for censorship and bias is being addressed with the creation of the Open Web Index as part of the Open Web Search project.

Although this addresses information retrieval, the presentation of the results in a way that does not cause information overload remains difficult. Keeping up with and reviewing content has become challenging, particularly in the scientific field, where the number of online publications keeps increasing and is quickly outpacing what simple search functions can make manageable. This task is further complicated by the fact that scientific articles are usually several pages long and require intensive analysis by the reader. The summarization of scientific articles is one way to make this process more efficient. However, the creation of manual summaries is just as time-consuming and can, furthermore, be subjective. This increases the need for an automated system that can generate precise, cohesive, and informative summaries.

This paper proposes a system intended for the summarization of long scientific documents, with particular emphasis being placed on accuracy, coherence, and transparency to create trustable summaries through the combination of a large language model with an explanation mechanism. The primary goal of this system is to help users efficiently acquire the most significant information from scientific papers for applications and use cases related to science search.

The resulting system was evaluated with two user studies which evaluated the quality of the summaries and the efficiency of the system's explanation functionality and intended to answer the following research questions:

RQ 1: How do authors evaluate the quality of the summaries generated by the AI system according to selected metrics?

RQ 2: Can this approach improve the transparency of the summary and does this influence user trust?

This paper will first give an overview of the background and related work, followed by a description of the system pipeline. Subsequently, two user studies will be discussed, as well as limitations of the proposed solution. In the last section, we consider possible future work and conclude the paper.

BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

The amount of data accessible on the Internet has expanded rapidly in recent years, leading to a need for methods to condense it into valuable information for users. This need for a strategy to manage this overload, as well as the introduction of the attention-based transformer model, as presented by Vaswani et al. [1], has had a significant influence on advances in the field of automatic summarization. Although initial research focused primarily on the production of brief summaries of news articles and the creation of corresponding datasets [2–4], the potential for further domains has been recognized, leading to further rapid developments in the field [5, 6].

Although the results have been promising and subsequent systems have found strong mainstream acceptance [7], problems remain before automatic summarization and large language models can be considered reliable and may be used in professional contexts. As deep learning techniques continue to advance in power and complexity, it becomes increasingly difficult to understand the reasoning behind the

results. However, this understanding is essential to assess the trustworthiness of the model. Hallucination, that is, the creation of text whose information is not implied by the source, can lead to misrepresentation of facts and mislead the user, making the results of these models inherently untrustworthy. Furthermore, it is generally unclear to the user what data the language model was trained on. This prevents the evaluation of potential biases in the data or the resulting model [8]. Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) focuses on addressing these issues by highlighting the need to clarify the decision-making processes used by complex AI models and improving the comprehensibility and transparency of black-box models [9]. This can be done in several ways.

Feature-importance-based methods use character-level features [10], n-grams [11], or latent features [12] to calculate the relevance of the feature to the result. Alternatively, a simple, more transparent model can be trained on results and then used to explain the original model's behavior. An example that makes use of this approach is *Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations* (LIME), which does so locally for single predictions [13].

Other systems use different approaches: QUINT utilizes provenance-based explainability to explain reasoning; the decision process is described to the user. It does so by visualizing the sequence of actions between the user's natural language input and the system's response [14]. ESCA, on the other hand, uses a more direct approach that also enables the user to intervene to direct the process if necessary. It produces explainable results by communicating centrality, sentence interactions, and attribute scores such as novelty and relevance to the user, showing impressive results compared to state-of-the-art models [15]. Another system, *explAIner* [18], uses TensorBoard and extends it by embedding explainers and enabling the execution of explainability methods at run-time. Visualizing the decision process is done using graphs.

Another approach to facilitate explainability of a result is to link back to the information source or sources for the different parts of the summary. Norkute et al. proposed a system for the use with legal document summarization [19]. They compared the attention vector approach with the source attribution approach and evaluated the effect they had on the trustworthiness of the results, as well as the effect on editor efficiency.

Attention highlighting was found to considerably speed up the review process, while source highlighting did not have a significant effect on this task. There was a similar conclusion for trustworthiness - while attention highlighting more closely mirrored how editors would go about summarizing documents and thus made users more confident that the whole document was considered by the system and increased trust because of it, source highlighting did not have this effect.

However, although promising, the second approach only included two editors who reviewed the system and needs to be evaluated in more settings and with a larger test group to be considered reliable.

SYSTEM DESIGN

Similarly to the systems described above, facilitating the explainability of the result was an essential aspect for the creation of this summarization system. To create explainable summaries, there were multiple steps in the process that needed to be addressed. Since the input was PDF files, processing them to create usable data for training and testing was an essential first step. Text extraction, cleaning of this extracted text, and sentence segmentation are considered to be part of this.

The next stage focused on the summarization process, which consisted of further pre-processing tasks via chunking and tokenizing, as well as the actual summarization step. Due to the need for a high maximum token count to summarize scientific articles, the choice of language model was limited. Subsequently, the explainability of the summary is addressed. Figure 1 shows a simplified representation of the system architecture.

Focusing on the approaches proposed by Norkute et al. [19] due to the available evaluation results, the source highlighting approach was chosen in the first step. This allowed for a comparison of the effect of the approach on legal summarization uses versus scientific summarization applications.

For the different steps of implementation, we made use of a variety of existing tools to simplify the process. The user interface itself uses Gradio to facilitate the upload of PDF files. Following this, the entire document text is extracted using the PDFMiner library. References and bibliographic entries are excluded, and any headings are marked to simplify later steps in the process.

As previously mentioned, large language models have a given maximum sequence length that the input cannot exceed - usually, any text surpassing this limit will be truncated. The exact number of tokens depends on the chosen model; it was with this in mind that the selection was made for this case. Scientific articles are usually many pages long, which limited the number of possibilities. The final selection was the Llama-2-7b-Chat model, which, although it supports input lengths of up to 4096 tokens, could not handle full-length scientific articles. Due to this, the text was first segmented to fit the token limit, taking care to set chunk overlap to 50 characters to facilitate the retention of context and continuity. Each of these text chunks is then fed to the language-model pipeline supplied by HuggingFace, resulting in a summary that is aggregated into a full-text summary.

The Explainable AI module, whose aim is to facilitate explainability of the created summary, functions by finding the most similar sentence from the source text for each summary sentence and presenting it to the user. Once again, the first step is tokenization, both for the original text and the generated summary. Special care was taken to recognize commonly used abbreviations such as "etc." as non-terminating entities. Following this, semantic analysis takes place using the SBERT based language models provided by SentenceTransformers as hosted on HuggingFace.

Figure 1: A simplified representation of the system architecture and its core components. From "Summarizing Long Scientific Documents: Leveraging Llama2-7B-Chat with Explainable AI" by S. Schäffer, p. 53. Adapted with permission [16].

Within these experiments, the all-MiniLM-L6-v2 model was found to have the best balance of performance and speed. Using mean pooling for standardizing the vector representations of the sentences incorporates the meaning of the entire sentence. Finally, the similarity between the sentences is calculated by using cosine similarity. The highest similarity score is returned to the user.

STUDY DESIGN, FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Two studies were carried out to evaluate the described explainability system, both using user feedback used to measure the quality of the results. In accordance with RQ 1, the first study asked the authors of the summarized papers to evaluate summary quality in a number of metrics. The second study evaluates the impact on the explainability method and how it impacts trustability in users, as well as overall summary quality metrics, as posed in RQ 2. For this evaluation, a variety of users were asked to rate the applicable metrics on a Likert scale of 1 to 5.

Author Study

For this study, we used the described system to create 20 summaries of articles published in the Journal of University Computer Science (J.UCS). The associated 68 authors were invited to evaluate the generated summaries using Likert scales. Of these, 11 authors answered the questionnaire.

As seen in Table 1, accuracy was generally rated well, with a majority of the participants rating this aspect 4 out of 5, with the last choosing 5. Both the highlighting of key contributions and the general coherence of the summaries displayed high variation in their ratings, indicating some level of inconsistent performance in the summarization process and inconsistent quality of the resulting summary. Nevertheless, general satisfaction with the summaries was rated medium to high.

In addition to these criteria, users were asked to rate the length of the generated summary. Of the 11 participants who answered the questionnaire, six found the summary length appropriate (3), three rated it "a bit too long" (4) and one person each considered it "a bit too short" (2) and "too long" (5), respectively.

Finally, participants were invited to provide feedback via free text. The responses given in this section indicated that

secondary information, such as acknowledgments, should be excluded from the generated summaries, as well as that some summaries displayed a high degree of redundancy.

Explainability Study

The second study focused on the functionality of the system's explainability module. Participants were asked to rate the explainability features to evaluate how they affected subjective user trust in the result. Unlike the first study, in this case anyone was welcome to participate. The evaluation was completed by 34 people, 33 (97.1%) of them between 18 and 34, and 1 (2.9%) between 45 and 54 years old. They came from various educational backgrounds, with 6 participants (17.6%) being high school graduates, 20 (58.8%) having a bachelor's degree, 6 (17.6%) with a master's degree, and two (5.9%) with a completed doctorate, covering a variety of demographics. Seven participants (20.6%) indicated that they considered themselves experienced (4) with artificial intelligence tools. The majority (15 participants; 44.1%) stated moderate experience (3), 11 (32.4%) considered themselves inexperienced, and one participant (2.9%) alleged that they had no experience. This range of experience levels means that the system was reviewed from a variety of points of view.

Users were provided with a brief description of the system, including images, as well as a YouTube video explaining its use. In the next step, they were asked to review the summaries with their respective source fragments according to a variety of criteria specified in Table 2.

The evaluation scores were generally high and all metrics received scores of 3 and 4 out of 5 from the majority of participants. The trust in the accuracy of the summary was scored the lowest, with a mean of 3.41, but a median of 3. This indicates that the transparency may not be sufficient with the used visualisation technique, or the quality of summaries insufficient, overall.

As in the previous study, participants received a free text question that allowed them to provide additional feedback. Multiple participants noted the increased time efficiency of automatic summarization, as well as the clarity and structure of the results and their direct comparison to portions of the source text, which they felt increased the level of trust towards the system.

Metric	Very low	Low	Moderate	High	Very high	Mean	Stdev
Accuracy	1	1	0	6	3	3.82	1.25
Key contributions	1	1	2	3	4	3.73	1.35
Coherence	1	1	4	4	1	3.27	1.10
Overall satisfaction	1	0	3	5	2	3.64	1.12

Table 1: Author evaluation of quantitative evaluation criteria on a scale from 1 (Very low) to 5 (Very high)

Metric	Very low	Low	Moderate	High	Very high	Mean	Stdev
Clarity	0	1	5	21	7	4.00	0.69
Trust in accuracy	1	3	15	11	4	3.41	0.91
Explainability	0	2	7	13	12	4.03	0.89
Coherence	0	2	4	17	11	4.09	0.82
Effect on trust	0	3	4	20	7	3.91	0.82
Interaction support	0	1	7	18	8	3.97	0.75

Table 2: User evaluation of metrics regarding summary quality such as clarity and coherence, as well as metrics evaluating the effectiveness of the explainability module using a scale from 1 (Very low) to 5 (Very high)

In contrast, the participants mentioned that the sentences did not read as a cohesive text, stating that they were lacking cohesiveness. Furthermore, the writing was considered monotonous, with repetitive sentence structures and wording. Multiple participants questioned the reliability of the system, one stating that the summarization may omit important facets of the source text and another suggesting that the lack of critical view may impact assumptions of a reader.

Discussion

Both studies involved a limited number of participants (11 and 34, respectively) which only allows for tentative conclusions. However, some interesting points can be made. Looking at the metric *Coherence*, which was rated by both the authors (see Table 1) and the general users (Table 2), it can be seen that the evaluation mean varies quite significantly, with the authors appearing to have higher expectations for the summaries than the users. This makes sense as the authors of the papers have a better overview of the full content of the papers they wrote. However, what also needs to be considered is what (if any) role subjectivity may play in this situation.

In general, the authors rated the quality of the summaries moderate to high, with a significant standard deviation in all evaluated metrics. This answers RQ 1 and implies that greater consistency in summary quality is necessary for this system to improve acceptance among authors.

The explainability module was very well received by the users in the user study, gaining high results on average. The question posed by RQ 2, how this approach influences user trust, was answered with a "high" by 58.82% of participants. The trust in accuracy was not rated as highly, which indicates that although the increased transparency of the summary did have an influence, it did not have a significant enough impact on some participants. This metric also had the highest standard deviation, which shows this disagreement among the participants.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper describes a system that intends to summarize scientific articles in a transparent and reliable way. To this end, it looks at the problem from two perspectives: that of the author and of the general user. The research questions were posed accordingly: Is the summary quality high enough to be acceptable for the authors? Do the users feel more secure in the summary due to the transparency increasing methods and how does this affect user trust?

The system that was created, as well as the two studies that were conducted in the course of this research, aimed to investigate these topics by assessing the performance of automatic summarization twofold. On the one hand, the created summaries were evaluated, while on the other hand, the explainability module was examined. Although the first results showed promising findings, the variation in responses for both studies indicates that more work is needed before such a system can be considered reliable, particularly in the two areas of summary quality and transparency-increasing measures.

Future work may focus on evaluating different visualization methods for the similarity score to facilitate explainability and trustability to an even higher degree. Furthermore, different language models can be used in the explainable AI module, as well as in the summarization module. Finally, it may be useful to provide not only the most similar sentence to the user but multiple sentences, as well as a confidence score, depending on the target audience of the system.

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